

Summary

This study explored how the brain helps us decide when unsure what will happen next. We focused on a brain network called the Default Mode Network (DMN), which is usually linked to daydreaming, recalling memories, and imagining the future. We wanted to understand how the DMN uses memories of past choices and rewards to guide future decisions. We analyzed brain activity from participants' brain images while they played a gambling game where they made decisions with uncertain outcomes. We found that, in some participants, DMN activity reflected past decisions, suggesting that the DMN helps track and evaluate previous experiences to guide future behavior. However, the gambling task had limitations for this study, so we recommend using better tasks in future research to better understand how the DMN supports decision-making.